

A Comparative Study between Sensory Shopping and Online Shopping of Gold Jewelry in Bengaluru

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Abstract

Gold jewelry is always considered auspicious and valuable product in Indian society. Most of them look forward to gold shopping as it is an investment. This study is conducted to understand the consumer’s opinion on gold jewelry shopping between the sensory and online shopping modes. The objective is to understand the impact of digitalization on gold jewelry shopping in Bengaluru amongst educated population and to compare the consumer’s opinions. The study also discusses various factors that affect the consumers shopping mode decision. It brings light to the online gold jewelry marketers and gives further suggestions to push online portals for gold jewelry shopping.

Keywords: Sensory Shopping, Online Shopping, Consumer’s Opinion, Jewelry Marketers.

Introduction

There is huge impact of digitalization on all industries helping to grow Indian economy rapidly. In such fast growing digital world where people can access to technology, internet and the educated population of the society most often prefers e-commerce portals only, equally in gold industry there are multiple certified brands like kalyan, Malabar jewelers, Tanishq and Joyalukas etc. selling gold jewelry online but even now people believe in traditional shopping method due to the stereotype mindset of Indians where gold is considered as an investment and should be bought from only trusted sellers. This study focuses on how far the sensory shopping (i.e. using the human senses to understand the touch, feel and look of the product) can be taken over by online shopping (that is use of internet and technology) in gold jewelry shopping. Is the Indian society ready to purchase gold online? How far the concept of e-commerce work in selling gold online in Bangalore? And bring out the factors that affect the purchase decision of the consumer.

Review of Literature

For purpose of this study around 36 literature was reviewed out of which the few main reviews are mentioned pertaining to the title of the paper.

Manek, J., & Khaparde, R. (2012). “Consumer buying behavior towards online jewelry shopping” in this article the author clearly explains the change of customer’s preference in online jewelry shopping which gives the details of buying behavior of customers. He also suggests the parameter to be kept in mind for marketers to understand the market strategies and channelize the market dynamics of jewelry online industry.

Minneslota university (2013) “sensory appeals in jewelry industry” adding to the previous author the writer here stresses the importance of sensory appeal that using of sensory organs to gain the attention and understand the customer taste and preference and how the sensory has impact on purchase decision of the customer. And the sensory appeal can give growth to the jewelry industries.

Srivastava, MS Preeti (2013) A Study of Consumer Online Shopping Attitude and Behavior towards Jewelry adding to the previous researcher here the author tries to explain the fundamentals of online shopping and how the current generation customers attitude and behavior is towards shopping products online and also gives the statistical figures of attitude and behavior of people from different age groups and their purchase behavior.

Research Gap

There are several researches that were conducted to study the use of digitalization or technology in e-commerce portals. But a very few researches were conducted for jewelry shopping online and most of them were on artificial jewelry. Therefore I feel there is huge scope to see what the impact of digitalization is on gold jewelry shopping.

Objectives

- To understand the comparative opinions of consumers purchase decision between online and regular retail showrooms (sensory) for shopping of gold jewelry.
- To recommend the gold jewelry marketers corrective measures.

Significance

In the digital world where there is generalized statement that people in urban localities prefer online shopping where they are comfortable sitting at home and ordering their products in pajamas than personally going to stores and buying. Is this statement applicable to all the economy generating fields? This study is conducted to understand the customer preference in gold jewelry shopping in store verses online store.

Research Question

How far the technology and online markets have taken over the sensory shopping in gold jewelry purchase in a metropolitan city like Bengaluru where at least 80% of the population are literates and are aware of online shopping.

Research Methodology

For purpose of the study the both primary and secondary data was collected in city of Bengaluru.

Primary

The data was collected in direct personal interview through structured questionnaire format, where 5 big brands of jewelry showrooms were visited that is kalyan jewelers, Tanishq jewelers, Malabar gold, Joyalukas and Bh ma jewelers were selected on a criteria that these stores have both physical setting and online portal to buy gold jewelry.

A systematic convenient method of sampling was adopted to choose the customers from the customers records of these 5 brands and around 115 samples were interviewed based on how many have purchased the jewelry in showroom and online. A set of fixed questions were asked to the customers out of which 100 were considered genuine for purpose of research.

Secondary

The data was collected from online sources, magazines, journals and newspapers.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data for the study was collected based on four main variables to understand the consumer’s preference in shopping that is based on selection, price, value and services. Here I have brought out the various factors and reasons to know the consumers purchase behavior and the medium used to purchase gold.

The first variable of the study is selection of the purchase mode. When interviewed the common opinion of individuals are as follows when gold is purchased in showroom the options of design is limited to stores only and there is possibility of required patterns, designs and products stock not available. On the other hand there is always a good clarity to the customer in terms of buying the jewelry after receiving the complete information and also the customers gets the whole look, touch and feel of the gold jewelry. Whereas purchasing gold in online is more comfortable and easily accessible anytime anywhere. There is always wide range of collection available in online portals and it is very easy for the customers to know if the product is o stock. The major disadvantage of online shopping is that the photoshoot high definition pictures vary from the original products there are also chances of fake websites selling gold online and misleading the customers.

The second variable of the study is price when gold being purchased in showrooms the prices can be negotiated as there is direct relationship between the buyer and seller. But there is always pressure of sales man in purchasing the jewelry. Whereas in online shopping the pricing is always rigid. Most of the portals offer price comparison which makes it easy for consumers. Here the customers are allowed to safe any number of items in kart without the pressure of salesman but clarifying any doubts regarding the product is time consuming.

The third variable for the study is value here, value refers to intangible services. In regular stores the services are usually taken care systematically with multiple offers attached to the product at the time of purchase like making charges, wastage , warranty and also provide after sale services to the customers by collecting personal information of the customer and wishing them on their birthdays or wedding anniversary reminding them to buy gold jewelry for their loved ones by doing this they will be able to build a good relationship with the customer and therefore expand their sales horizons. Whereas in online portals there is no direct link between the buyer and seller. There is no guarantee of who is selling the jewelry. In case of any issues the claims and services are time consuming. The most common issue is not all sellers are authorized and poor after sales services.

The fourth variable of the study is services. Services are well managed in physical stores as the customer feels he / she is treated royally. The customer is explained each and every aspect of the jewelry and the customer has an added advantage of touching and feeling the product and know how it looks and is sure about the product before purchase. In showrooms the after sales services such as professional cleaning, sizing or repair is more easily accessible whereas in online selling the customers feel that they are most often mislead by high resolution pictures and deliver average products. But these portals have a good feature of live chat where the person is allowed to clarify or enquiry about the products. Also the shopping is not limited to any time or place constraint therefore it’s very easy to shop.

Findings

1. Education: 71% of the consumers are UG graduates, 17 % are post graduates and 12% are non-graduates.
2. Gender: 46 are men and 54 are women customers.
3. 90% of the consumers are aware of online gold jewelry shopping portals and still prefer regular retail shops for purchase.
4. 11% of consumers have preferred online shopping portals that is caratlane.in for reasons such as emergency shopping, less time consuming, wide range of designs available and due to special occasion and festival offers.
5. 61% of consumers say that it's always in online portals that they have wide range of products choice and designs, but are not guaranteed with the quality and product in HD pictures differing from the product that has been delivered to the customers.
6. 92% of individuals prefer purchasing gold jewelry from normal shops as the “trust” factor plays an important role in making the investment decision.
7. 67% of consumers prefer store shopping for ‘customer service, immediate rectification of problems, good customer relationship and for seller guarantee’.
8. 73% of people feel that buying gold from regular retail shops can be more affordable as the price can be negotiated as the customers and dealer have direct relationship.
9. 46% of consumer feel that shopping in regular stores can reduce the cost of purchase as the delivery or shipping charges can be avoided.
10. 93% of consumers feel that purchasing in retail shops is more safe than shopping online as the there is no direct link between the buyer and seller.
11. 53% of consumers feel that online shopping may be accessible at anytime and anywhere but is definitely more time consuming as delivery takes time and is very complex to connect to the seller after sales for any exchange, repair, refund of payment, clarifying payment issues or any other product related issues.
12. 89% of people prefer sensory shopping as it gives a clear picture to the buyer how the product exactly looks and does it suit the customers which is not possible when the customer shops it online.
13. The study shows that there is no relationship between a person's educational qualification and his gold shopping purchase decision.

Conclusion

The study states that the current generation is more enthusiastic with shopping online using technology, internet, electronic gadgets and apps available on mobiles. Irrespective of age, gender, income and different socio-economic standards 93% of people are interested to shop online the products such as daily necessities, food products, artificial jewelry, household goods, clothing, stationary, electronic gadgets etc. The products like gold which is considered as investment aspect for most of the Indian families which is expensive and is purchased during some special occasions are always paid more attention in terms of purchase decision. The research clearly shows that an individual prefers sensory shopping over the online shopping for purchasing gold jewelry for several reasons such as, the consumers feel safer and secure in sensory shopping. They are surer about the look and feel of the product. Most of the consumers enjoy the royal treatment given to them during the time of shopping. The level of satisfaction of consumers is comparatively high in sensory shopping than that of online shopping as the consumer possess all the information regarding the product. The price of the jewelry can be negotiated, the customers are sure of the dealer and is guaranteed of their jewelry. Even though a wide range of variety is available for the

customers with click of a button still the customers prefer sensory shopping as they can customize the designs and are sure of the product description. In this research it is also proved that the level of customer satisfaction is higher in sensory shopping as the after sales service is resolving the customers issue is less time consuming and is taken care systematically and is easily resolved whereas in online shopping the grievance resolve portals are complex procedure to understand by the customer.

To conclude individuals are more interested in shopping inexpensive or daily necessities in online than shopping a gold jewelry which is expensive. So as a result the other online e-commerce portals have greater chance of business. On contrary to this the gold online portal performance is bit low.

Limitations

- The study is limited to city of Bengaluru only.
- The sample size is limited to particular population only.

Recommendations

1. It is important for the jewelry marketers to create awareness to the customer’s regarding the online gold shopping portals.
2. Since ‘trust’ is one common factor which is common opinion of individuals for not choosing online shopping. The marketers need to build the trust factor to the customers by improving their customer services.
3. The jewelry brands should focus on more of advertising the online shopping to the customers as the showrooms can save a lot of money in infrastructure and interiors.
4. Online website companies need to communicate about the positive aspects such as less making charges, built up a trust factor, more availability of designs and assurance of quality and many other aspects that can attract the consumer.
5. Time factor such as 24hrs online shopping, with all the other flexibilities of mode of payment can play vital role for companies to pull consumers towards online shopping.

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